

D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan (update)

**WP6 Enabling environment and
awareness raising**

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Executive summary

The purpose of the Deliverable D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan (update) is to update, revise where necessary and refine the dissemination and communication strategy that has been and will be followed, as well as to elaborate on the project's dissemination and communication activities that have been and will be executed throughout the duration of the project. In more detail, the present document provides an update and to the D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan that was submitted in M04 of the project, and further defines the strategy, activities and tools which the DIANA project will use to disseminate the project results and to communicate with the wider public.

It shall be noted that effective dissemination and communication activities are of major importance to the DIANA project, paving the way for the successful exploitation and “users’ adoption” of the project outputs (products, services, policy suggestions etc.) during and following the project completion.

Thus, the DIANA consortium is committed to continuously revise and refine the dissemination and communication plan and actions, allocating significant effort, ensuring the effective dissemination and communication of the project.

The updates/revisions of the current document are based on the experience gained by the consortium during the 1st year of the project, especially through the consortium involvement with the targeted user groups and related stakeholders.

1. Introduction

The core objective of DIANA Dissemination and Communication strategy is to fulfil the need to disseminate the concept, methodologies, best practices and lessons learnt from the pilots and project outcomes to the local community or communities, but also to communicate the added value to the wider public. DIANA project aims to implement a comprehensive and “target user group” oriented dissemination and communication strategy in order to:

- Raise awareness and provide high visibility of the project;
- Establish a strong brand identity from the beginning;
- Encourage involvement of water-framework related stakeholders;
- Raise awareness of policy makers and public bodies;
- Facilitate synergies with similar or complementary initiatives;
- Promote, implement and spread the use of the delivered services; and
- Prepare the ground for the successful exploitation and commercialisation of all DIANA project outputs (products, services, policy framework, etc.), among and beyond currently defined target groups.

In the following sections we are going to describe the context of the DIANA project, the strategy that is going to be followed (methodology, objectives, expected results), the target groups and audiences, the dissemination and communication tools that the consortium is going to use, as well as some of the foreseen actions that will be taken during and after the end of the project, the role of the project partners, the monitoring and evaluation of the plan and finally the schedule and action planning.

2. DIANA core-concept

Agriculture accounts for approximately a quarter of the 182 billion m³ of water extracted every year in Europe. This substantial amount of abstracted EU water is used predominantly for irrigation since it is a common practice in agriculture aimed at improving crop productivity, reducing risks of crop failures due to dry periods and stabilising yields. At the same time, however, irrigation is also a major cause of non-authorized water (over-)abstraction, or in other words the abstraction of volumes of water that are larger than officially permitted and/or sustainably available, thus imposing increasing pressures on the sustainability of European water resources. With this in mind and given the scarcity of our water resources as well as the fact that drought is becoming an increasingly frequent phenomenon across Europe¹, it is evident that novel and innovative solutions are required in order to address these threatening problems that EU waters are currently facing. In this respect, the latest advances in Earth Observation (EO) pose an unprecedented opportunity to develop commercial services for EU water authorities to control and deal with these problems in a cost-effective and systematic manner.

It is quite surprising that in most of the cases, the method that is currently being used to detect and monitor non-authorized water abstractions is through the traditional time-consuming and costly field inspections carried out by experienced professionals in correlation with existing water rights databases and more often than not on a random basis. However, this method incorporates significant costs, it is hindered by the limited availability of human and financial resources required for carrying out extensive inspections, is not possible to achieve given the number of users and the difficulty to access private properties and to detect tampering or maintenance problems².

The overarching objective of DIANA is to co-create, co-design and demonstrate in real operational environments a commercial service platform that will empower water management authorities to optimise the identification and inspection of non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation as well as significantly improve the monitoring and assessment of their water management policies and practices, both in standard and special conditions such as in cases of drought. DIANA

¹ Droughts are long term imbalance resulting from water demand exceeding available water resources and may occur anywhere in Europe including high as well as low rainfall areas regardless of seasons.

² Water Over-abstraction and Illegal Water Abstraction Detection and Assessment (WODA) – phase 2, European Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law (IMPEL), Guidance document, 2017.

will leverage Earth Observation (EO) data as well as state-of-the-art models for the identification of (illegally) irrigated areas and the estimation of abstracted water volumes in order to offer a demand-driven suite of data products and services that will be affordable, cost-effective and of high added value, mainly but not exclusively, due to the:

- Enhanced temporal and spatial resolution of the Sentinel satellites which provide EO data on a free, open and full access basis. This enables DIANA to drastically reduce service costs by avoiding the use of expensive commercial satellite imagery, while achieving large geographic coverage with great accuracy.
- Systemisation and optimisation of monitoring and inspections: continuous monitoring and calibrated measurement will better guide field inspections to areas where infringements are more likely to be taking place, thus greatly increasing the efficiency and decreasing the costs of mapping and monitoring irrigated areas. This will lead to the re-direction of a considerable portion of the already scarce human and financial resources of public authorities towards other activities.
- Minimisation of the in-house resources, infrastructure and skills required for effectively employing EO data to manage their water resources more sustainably: DIANA customers will not have to purchase and install any additional equipment or have any special technical/informatics background to benefit from the provided services.

DIANA services will apply to different types of non-authorized water abstractions including (i) abstractions of water aimed at irrigating areas without official water rights as well as (ii) water abstractions beyond the volumes allowed by relevant authorities (either constantly or during periods of special restrictions). Moreover, they will cover a multitude of suitable agricultural and operational contexts (e.g. in terms of types of irrigated crops, climate conditions, target area size, administrative, technical and financial capabilities of users, etc.). In addition, DIANA users will be able to leverage project value propositions in order to produce meaningful information for farmers (e.g. drought forecasts for crop planning and selection), enabling us to promote further socio-economic and environmental benefits to the European economy and society as a whole.

3. Dissemination and Communication Plan – update

This section provides a short analysis of the general Dissemination and Communication strategy based on the experience of the first 12 months of the project development and provides minor suggestions for improvement for the period of 2018-2019. The scope of the deliverable and of the current section, is not to provide a report on the Dissemination and Communication activities performed, these will be presented in detail in the next WP6 deliverable D6.6 Report on the results of dissemination activities (1) due in M18 as well as in the mid-technical report (M18), but to focus and present the Dissemination and Communication Plan and relative strategy updates/refinements, to be adopted by the project.

This section complements and updates Chapter 5 in the deliverable D6.1 Dissemination and communication Plan.

3.1. Dissemination and Communication strategy implemented (M0-M12)

During the first year of its implementation, the DIANA project has followed the Dissemination and Communication Plan as presented in the D6.1 Dissemination and communication Plan. During this period up to the submission date of the present deliverable, no major change has been required. Following the successful implementation of the 1st year, based on the experience gained by the consortium and early network connections and synergies established, only minor changes/additions to the initial plan have been discussed and are presented in this document. These minor alterations are the result of the first-year activities and the respective feedback received and aim to further strengthen the Dissemination and Communication impact.

At this point it shall be noted that even though the first version of the DIANA Dissemination and Communication Plan was delivered in M02, the actual activity started from the very beginning of the project by empowering the DIANA consortium in network activities with target communities and stakeholders.

All consortium partners committed to proactively communicate and disseminate project related content, both by lever their current network of contacts through their preferred traditional communication channels, and by engaging with and forming new networks of contacts in order to reach the largest possible EU-wide audience.

In addition to partners “sole networking” activities, the project consortium went some steps further and collaboratively initiated the formation of the DIANA Network of Interest (NoI) and DIANA Advisory Board (AB), two bodies that are expected to benefit the DIANA project awareness significantly.

The principal role of the AB is to act as a consultation and validation body for the project. The AB is comprised of both diverse representatives from DIANA user/stakeholder communities and leading experts in the fields of water management, space applications in agriculture, agricultural and environmental policies, irrigation engineering and business management who will provide advice for development of the project.

Due to the fact that DIANA partners are already involved and active in the water sector, the experts proposed for the AB had been anticipated and involved from a very early stage. Within that framework, the work package leader along with the partners decided to adopt a more flexible structure for the DIANA AB that consists in splitting the AB into a “Core Advisory Board” and “Thematic Advisory Groups” and/or “Country Advisory Groups” in order to exploit the different expertise to the maximum.

With regard to the NoI it should be noted that the pilots of DIANA, namely Sannio Alifano, Feragua and NARW (all three stakeholders in the domain) will be its cornerstone, since they are able to tap into their pool of members and networks to help disseminate DIANA’s results and showcase how they benefit from the outcomes of the project and how this could be of high importance to other similar stakeholders.

The establishment and formation of the aforementioned bodies, and their integration within the DIANA project, multiplies the project generated added value. As the project evolves and delivers more exploitable results, the consortium efforts will be continuous to further extend the number of the members-stakeholders involved and further extend dissemination and communication actions about project activities and assets, leveraging the related value propositions.

3.2. Project visual identity, exploitation and communication channels

Establishing a strong project visual identity and a well-defined branding strategy was a priority by the project consortium for ensuring effective dissemination and communication activities and

building a consistent image for the DIANA project. Thus, early in the project a strong visual identity was developed and the following components were delivered:

- *logo design* (see Figure 1)
- *fonts*
- *colours* (see Figure 2), *shapes and forms*

They were presented in detail in the deliverable D6.3 Promotional Material (M04).

Figure 1: DIANA logo

Blue Accent 94,177,229
Black 0,0,0
White-255,255,255
Grey Accent 3 80% Lighter 237,237,237

Figure 2: DIANA colour palette

Based on the DIANA Project logo and colour palette, a strong and coherent visual identity was applied to the various project related documents:

- Deliverable documents;
- Non-Deliverable Documents, such as memos, notes or letters;
- Deliverable document reviews;
- Event reports;
- Press releases;
- Presentations.
- Project Info Fact-Sheet
- Project Poster
- Project Brochure
- Project Leaflet

(for a more detailed presentation of the “full Project Visual identity” see deliverables D6.3 Promotional Material & D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan).

Having established a concrete project visual identity from the beginning allowed the consortium to initiate continuous and consistent dissemination activities, starting from the first events in which the project participated, and from the first publications issued.

This strong DIANA project visual identity will also enhance and assist all exploitation and commercialisation actions (performed or planned) within WP5, towards the successful commercial exploitation of the project outputs (products and services) and the creation of a DIANA branding during and beyond the lifespan of the project, in accordance with the DIANA exploitation and commercialisation plan and related activities.

3.3. Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Within the deliverable **D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan** a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) were proposed as shown in

. No changes have been implemented in the expected target values.

Table 1: DIANA key performance indicators

Performance Indicator	Target Value	Means of verification
Visitors to the project website	6.000	Google analytics
“Likes” on DIANA Facebook page	500	Facebook account data
Followers of DIANA on Twitter	300	Twitter account data
Members on LinkedIn group	200	LinkedIn account data
Number of viewers of audiovisual material on YouTube	1000	Number of views on YouTube
Publications on mass media	45	Dissemination reporting
Scientific publications	5	Dissemination reporting
Events to be attended by Project partners	10	Dissemination reporting
Newsletters produced	12	Copies available from reporting or via website
Number of subscribers to the newsletter	300	List of recipients
Number of contacts established in the Nol	200	List of stakeholders
Number of distributed printed material	2000	Dissemination reporting

The DIANA project performance with regards to the KPIs established will be provided in the deliverables D6.6 Report on the results of Dissemination activities (1) (M18) and D6.7 Report on the results of Dissemination activities (2) (M36) as well as in the technical report of the interim review.

3.4. Target groups and audiences

In the deliverable D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan the following main target audiences have been defined:

Table 2: Target groups and audiences

Target group	Activity of target group	Example
Water managers	Responsible for monitoring and inspecting abstractions of water for irrigation	Public authorities or associations of irrigators depending on national/regional particularities
Authorities	Responsible for developing and implementing water/drought management plans and/or the WDF as well as issue irrigation water rights	River basin authorities, regional or local authorities
Farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies	Active in the agricultural sector	Agribusiness professionals, advisors, innovation intermediaries
Research and Academia	Also with activities relevant to the agricultural sector	Academic institutions, non-university public research organisations, research and technology organisations
Non-governmental organisations and civic society groups	Interested in sustainable water management in the EU and aimed at addressing relevant social challenges and needs	Associations and NGOs
Other Stakeholders	That may be interested in project outcomes	Policy and decision makers at EU level, etc
Wider public	People that have an interest on the issue	People that have an interest on the issue

The aforementioned segmentation of the project target audience was performed aiming in the first place to achieve effective and efficient dissemination and communication around the project and its results, allowing the consortium to specialise dissemination and communication actions per audience type/target group and deliver a more efficient and attractive “dissemination profile” to each of the target groups. Moreover, the audience segmentation was created in order to maximise exploitation and commercialisation efficiency of DIANA project outputs.

This segmentation will be refined by means of co-creation workshops, which allow for “needs and requirements” within each of the target group audiences to be collected, analysed and afterwards aligned and transformed into better “potential customer profiling” and suggestions for service and/or product improvement (DIANA product/services refinement). Additionally, co-creation workshops are the means for disseminating DIANA to the targeted audience of Water Authorities.

Even though co-creation processes start with a minimum number of users, they are continuously increased, thus the visibility of the project is also improved.

4. DIANA Communication Channels and Tools

This section provides a brief overview of used communication channels and tools utilised so far, as well as future planning and directions.

4.1. Website

The DIANA website (<http://diana-h2020.eu/>) was released in M04 (as described in detail in the deliverable D6.5 DIANA Web Portal) and represents a central point of dissemination for all target audiences. At this stage, the website contains information about the project (structure, objectives, concept, team, etc.) and can be used as a communication tool that assists partners in reaching stakeholders, as well as the wider audience. The project website will be further populated during the 2nd year of the project, focusing on improving and expanding the general information already provided with additional content (news, activities, events, etc.). The aim is to deliver content that attracts and raises the number of unique and returning visitors.

Furthermore, for the 2nd year of the project a number of “Website related actions” are planned and include but are not limited to:

- creating a continuous flow of news/publications and information, targeting specific combinations of content and audience target group;
- improving the content with project practical outputs, best practices;
- including “practical abstracts” deriving from the co-creation workshops performed;
- populating website links with relative initiatives, projects and communicating about established and future synergies.

4.2. E-mail lists and Newsletter

DIANA mailing list is continuously populated with new contacts and members, both from the website subscription button (self-registered subscriptions) but also from the consortium continuous engagement and networking activities. DIANA project updates and an electronic copy of the DIANA newsletter will be circulated to the mailing list in order to maintain members’ interest, increase engagement with the DIANA “expanding” community and leverage word-of-mouth communication to perpetuate project objectives.

For the 2nd year of the project a number of upscaling-actions are planned and include, but are not limited to:

- circulating the 1st DIANA newsletter;
- further expanding DIANA email list with more members;
- including an interview with a “policy-decision maker” in each of the newsletters;
- communicating project outputs combined with actual case-studies.

4.3. Social Media

DIANA project has established a coherent social media presence, as described in detail in the deliverable D6.4 Social Media Accounts (M05). Active project accounts have been established in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, engaging and interacting with followers.

Using social networks allows the DIANA project not only to reach and communicate with a large group of people nearly instantly, but also to disseminate value generated to the wide public.

Based on the consortium experience gained during the 1st year of the project, and in parallel to the continuous evaluation of the impact and reach generated through the different social media, the consortium decided to further customise them and assign specific project material to be circulated through each social media account.

Thus the Facebook account will be used for “wide public” dissemination actions, Twitter for wide public dissemination and synergies with “water related” influencers (Twitter represents the most dynamic way of communicating and cross-posting relevant news that are either DIANA originals or relevant third party/other organisation posts, building in this way greater awareness), LinkedIn for “Experts and Scientific community” dissemination purposes and YouTube for disseminating video material to all audiences (a variation of video material will be provided to address the various audience target groups).

Social Media Channel	Main type of Material
Facebook	Engagement material, infographics, meeting pictures, practical abstracts etc.
Twitter	Relevant conferences and events material
LinkedIn	Public deliverables, scientific publications, White papers
YouTube	<i>Various</i>

This decision and respective actions plan will further strengthen awareness of the project, and increase audience reach and engagement by delivering "the right content to the right audience group".

4.4. Printable material

DIANA project holds a coherent portfolio of printable "marketing" material including: a project Poster, a project Leaflet, a project Brochure and a project Info Fact Sheet, as described in detail in the deliverable D6.3 Promotional Material (M06).

The first version of all printable material was already been disseminated to all partners and uploaded to the website. The translation of the relevant material, in the partners languages and especially in those of the pilot partners, has been initiated and is expected to end within the next few months of the project.

All printable material will be updated whenever necessary and in accordance with the project progress, ensuring that each material responds to the needs of specific stakeholders and groups of interest.

5. Next Dissemination and communication actions

The following sections outline the dissemination activities that have been planned and will be carried out in the scope of the DIANA project. *Table 3* below, though, first briefly presents the various project and dissemination interrelated activities as they were listed in the deliverable D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M04) and provides an overview of their current status.

Table 3 Interrelated project and dissemination activities

Project phase	Project Actions	Dissemination actions	Status
1 st to 2 nd year	Assess project characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding (logos, templates, etc) • Email lists and discussion forums and • Social networking tools 	☑
	Prepare deliverables ensuring that they are adaptable and findings can be easily found	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Printable material • Online repositories and other audio-visual material 	☑
	Articulate the value of the project outcomes and build credibility and familiarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participatory dissemination (partners) • Investigate for conferences, workshops, showcases of interest 	☑
	Identify potential adopters, assess their characteristics and identify other possible enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks and communities of practice • Email lists and discussion forums • Social networking tools • Meetings and discussions (mainly internal) roundtables and invited presentations (from external members: i.e. advisory board) 	☑
	Plan for interaction and response to changes and opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks and communities of practice • Email lists and discussion forums • Outline of newsletter 	☑

2nd to 3rd year	Support initial uptake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting and discussions with stakeholders from the pilot (and possibly other interested) areas • Presentations in workshops, events, conferences • Guides and material 	• Upcoming
	Support adoption and evaluation of the outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influencing policy • Networks and communities of practice • Media releases 	• Upcoming
Post project	Expand to different potential adopters outside the initial target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal articles and book chapters • Project final report • Webpages, online repositories, audio-visual material and other online content • Media releases 	• Upcoming

All planned actions for the 1st year of the project have been carried out successfully and in according to the plan (D6.1). All consortium partners took part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

In the following sections we examine all relevant activities planned for the 2nd year of the project.

5.1. Network of Interest

The establishment and management of DIANA Network of Interest (NoI) has been and will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. The main aim of establishing and expanding the “DIANA Network of Interest” is to have it act as a main dissemination pole for the engagement of DIANA target groups.

The DIANA NoI enables project partners to communicate the project objectives and disseminate its results on local, regional, national and European level. So far, the DIANA NoI counts 50 members (the number will be updated on D6.6 Report on the results of dissemination activities (1)). All NoI participants are encouraged to be involved in discussions concerning technical and

scientific issues of the project through the official DIANA website, and they will be invited to participate in the project policy workshops.

Even though the effort is and will be to expand the NoI members list as a whole, special attention is given to attract those members that have the intention and the potential to utilise the DIANA solution and, above all, to its future customers' base (those stakeholders who have the potential to purchase the solution).

5.2. Mass media communication

Obtaining news coverage, whether at national or local level, increases the profile of the project to a great extent and enables the consortium to reach a very wide audience. The aim is to continue and utilise mass media communication activities to inform the general public about the DIANA project.

The DIANA consortium intends to continue the dissemination of the project through TV and radio channels, web media, and newspapers and magazines - either printed or electronic ones. The DIANA partners are encouraged to disseminate the DIANA project through mass media on a regular basis.

5.3. Scientific publications

Project partners are encouraged to collaborate with each other and jointly prepare publications relevant to the DIANA project, since these represent an effective dissemination channel for addressing the scientific community. Scientific journals that provide open access (OA) to all their publications are preferred, as it is required by the European Commission.

The DIANA project has already issued a first publication titled **“Remote Sensing for Crop Water Management: From ET Modelling to Services for the End Users”** by *Alfonso Calera, Isidro Campos, Anna Osann, Guido D’Urso and Massimo Menenti*, on *Sensors 2017*, 17, 1104 and is expected to produce a sufficient number of publications in scientific, peer-reviewed journals during the 2nd year of the project.

5.4. Participation in events

Further to scientific publications, a secondary way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of project partners in targeted non-project events, such as scientific conferences and symposiums, where project as whole or specific actions and results of it (scientific knowledge and

methodologies emerging) can be presented. The participation of DIANA consortium partners to such events is foreseen also during the 2nd year of the project. An updated detailed list of conferences and symposiums relevant to DIANA project is available in ANNEX I – Targeted external non-project events. The list is being continuously updated with new conferences from the WP leader and all the beneficiaries. Partners’ representatives are encouraged to participate in major conferences of relevant fields presenting the DIANA project and related scientific results.

Furthermore, DIANA project partners are encouraged to participate in key workshops in the fields of irrigation, agriculture, precision agriculture, Earth Observation throughout the duration of the project in order to increase the project’s visibility and keep building the DIANA contact list and the Network of Interest. Furthermore, other Open Events such as Agricultural Fairs with a focus on new technologies and irrigation or Shows with similar subjects will be also useful means to disseminate the DIANA project in different target audiences than those attended workshops.

Informal networking

Further to the “formal” Networking actions performed by partners, a number of informal networking activities are taking place, mainly through the participation in relevant events linked to the project theme. All networking activities formal and informal aim to increase project awareness and strengthen exploitation strategy. DIANA project partners are encouraged to participate in such events.

Advisory Board

The Advisory Board is an integral part of DIANA project and its establishment assists the DIANA project to have access to valuable knowledge and expertise at all stages of the project implementation. Within that framework and as mentioned above DIANA is going to deploy both a Core AB and Thematic and/or Country ABs in order to fully exploit the expertise offered by the nominees that are part of the existing network of the partners. The table below shows all nominees suggested by DIANA partners:

Table 4: Nominees for DIANA AB

No.	Name	Institution
1	Mircea Sevastel – Land Reclamation Engineer, Professor	University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Bucharest, Faculty of Land Reclamation and Environmental Engineering

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2	Catalin Lazar	National Agricultural Research and Development Institute Fundulea, Romania
3	Violeta Florian	Scientific Researcher, Institute of Agricultural Economics, Romanian Academy
4	Diana Dogaru	Scientific Researcher, Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy
5	Viorel Chendes	Scientific Director, National Institute of Hydrology and Water Management, Romania
6	Roberto Iodice	Hydraulic engineer, official of italian Ministry of Agriculture
7	Antonino Casciolo	Hydraulic engineer, retired official of italian Ministry of Agriculture
8	Dott. Massimo Gargano	General Manager at A.N.B.I.
9	Dott. Vito Busillo	Board Memeber of National Association of Irrigation and Reclamation Consortia (A.N.B.I.)
10	Dott. Agr. Giuseppe Castaldi	Excecutive of Regional Department of Agriculture
11	Ing. Nicola Meddalena	General Manager of CIHEAM-IAMB
12	Dario Scaella	Entrepreneur, CEO di K4A srl, president of CHAI consortium (Campania Helicopters and Airplane industry NETwork) and board member of CIRA (Italian Aerospace Research Center)
13	Raffaella Zucaro	Researcher from Council for Agricultural Research and Economy Analysis (CREA)
14	Andreas Panagopoulos	Soil and Water Resources Institute
15	TBA	Expert from Ministry of Environment
16	TBA	Expert from Ministry of Agriculture
17	Fabio Vescovi	Airbus, EO/ICT Copernicus
18	Bettina Baruth	JRC
19	TBA	Representative of DG Environment

Furthermore it should be noted that the Advisory Board acts as an additional dissemination channel, promoting the project results, helping to identify and better understand key target groups, as well as reach them. Finally it can help in the creation and further development of the Network of Interest. Being a part of the sector and being respectable in their fields, the members

of the Advisory Board can well help in that last aspect as well as empower DIANA exploitation and business cases with valuable insight.

6. Concluding Remarks

The present deliverable contains the proposed update of the Dissemination and Communication Plan; all suggestions and new guidelines are based on the results and experience gained following the 1st year of implementing the DIANA project and the relative impact of all performed dissemination activities, to date.

An analysis of the activities performed up to date, allows the consortium to feel confident of the effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication roadmap established with D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan. Thus, no major changes were required when updating initial plan in the frame of the present deliverable.

It shall be noted that deliverable D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan (update) contains only updated sections of and defines minor changes to the initial document, deliverable D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan, in an attempt to translate intra-consortium decisions to actions for an even more efficient and effective Dissemination and Communication strategy.

Finally, the present document provides an comprehensive list of conferences and events for the 2nd year of the project (ANNEX I: Targeted external non-project events).

Appendix A

ANNEX I: Targeted external non-project events

Event	Short Description	Link
Salon des maires et des collectivités locales 2017	Exhibition dedicated to Mayors and Local Authorities - the great French meeting for public procurement	http://www.salondesmaires.com/
World efficiency 2017	Expo & congress for Climate & Ressources. The World Efficiency show is an exhibition of solutions allowing professionals to preserve resource (saving, optimization and diversification solutions) and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (low carbon solutions)	https://www.world-efficiency.com/en/Home/
HYDROGAÏA	Water Conference and Trade Exhibition	http://www.hydrogaia-expo.com/
IFAT	International Trade Fair for Environment, Waste Water and Waste Disposal	http://www.ifat.de/index-2.html
ABWASSER.PRAXIS	Congress with trade fair dedicated exclusively to the topic of wastewater	http://www.abwasserpraxis.de/
2017 Irrigation Show & Education Conference	The Irrigation Show and Education Conference is where the irrigation industry comes together to network and learn	http://www.irrigation.org/irrigationshow/
AQUATECH AMSTERDAM	International Trade Exhibition of Water Technology and Water Management	http://www.eventseye.com/fairs/f-aquatech-amsterdam-122-1.html
SIGA	Spain's International Water Industry Fair. For Innovative Water Management Solutions	http://www.ifema.es/siga_06
AGWATEC SPAIN	International Agriculture & Water Technology Exhibition & Conference	http://agwatec.es/
EXPO ALCADIA	Show of Equipment and Services for Municipalities and Territorial Entities	http://www.feriazaragoza.com/events
SMAGUA	International Water Exhibition	http://www.smagua.com/
8TH WORLD WATER FORUM	The World Water Forum is the world's biggest water-related event and is organized by the World Water Council (WWC), an international organization that brings together all those interested in the theme of water.	http://www.worldwaterforum8.org/production.worldwaterforum8.org/en
World Water Week	World Water Week is the annual focal point for the globe's water issues. It is organized by SIWI. In 2018, World Water Week will address the theme "Water, ecosystems and human development".	http://www.worldwaterweek.org/
Wasser Berlin International	Wasser Berlin International is Germany's specialized, international marketing platform for water.	https://www.wasser-berlin.de/en/About/
Global Water Summit	The Global Water Summit has always been about connections: water meets money, public meets private, business meets opportunity. In 2018 we will focus on how cross-cutting issues emerging from the boundaries of the sector may drive performance and generate new	http://www.watermeetsmoney.com/

D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan (update)

	opportunities for businesses who are ready to build and engage with the new models and stakeholders	
European Water Tech Week Leeuwarden 2018	The global water technology sector is increasingly organized in hubs. The European Water Tech Week Leeuwarden 2018 (EWTW 2018) will connect these hubs in Leeuwarden, the United Nations Innovating City for water technology.	http://watercampus.nl/en/nieuws/european-water-tech-week-leeuwarden-2018/

